
Fractal-Based Modeling of Coal Permeability under Water Injection Based on CT-Derived Microstructure

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Abstract: Coal seam water injection is strongly influenced by the microstructural characteristics of coal, which control fluid flow behavior within pore–fracture systems. In this study, coal samples from the No. 15 coal seam were characterized using X-ray computed tomography (CT) combined with image processing and pore network extraction. Key parameters, including effective porosity, pore throat radius, and fractal dimensions, were quantitatively obtained. Based on fractal theory, a permeability model was developed by incorporating pore size distribution and flow path tortuosity. The volumetric fractal dimension and tortuosity fractal dimension were introduced to describe structural complexity and flow path irregularity, respectively, establishing a quantitative relationship between microstructure and permeability. Model validation was performed by comparing calculated permeability with experimental results from water injection tests. The results show good agreement, with an average relative error of 8.92%, indicating reliable predictive performance. The analysis further reveals that permeability increases with effective porosity and pore throat radius, while decreasing with increasing fractal dimensions. This study provides a quantitative framework for linking coal microstructure to permeability behavior.

Keywords: Coal seam water injection; Permeability model; Fractal theory; Pore network; Computed tomography

1. Introduction

Coal seam water injection is an important technical measure for dust suppression and gas control in underground coal mining. A large number of studies have shown that water injection can effectively reduce dust concentration and improve the safety of mining operations^[1-4]. In addition, the development, application, and optimization of water injection technologies have been extensively investigated under different geological and engineering conditions^[5-6], and early studies have provided a systematic understanding of mine dust prevention and control^[7]. To further improve injection performance, researchers have explored parameter optimization methods and enhancement techniques, such as multi-index decision-making approaches^[8] and the use of surfactants to improve coal wettability^[9-10]. These studies indicate that both operational parameters and fluid–coal interactions play key roles in determining the effectiveness of water injection.

Despite these advances, most existing studies focus on engineering applications and empirical optimization, while the fundamental relationship between coal microstructure and permeability remains insufficiently clarified. Since permeability is essentially controlled by the internal pore–fracture system, it is necessary to investigate coal from a microstructural perspective. With the development of imaging technologies, X-ray computed tomography (CT) has been widely used to characterize the three-dimensional structure of porous media. Lindquist *et al.*^[11] and Liang *et al.*^[12] analyzed pore geometry and topology based on high-resolution images, while Silin *et al.*^[13] proposed pore network extraction methods using maximal inscribed spheres. In addition, fluid transport and dust migration processes in coal mining environments have been studied through

experimental and numerical approaches, further highlighting the importance of permeability in controlling flow behavior^[14-15].

Fractal theory provides an effective framework for describing the complexity and heterogeneity of porous media. However, existing studies often focus either on structural characterization or on permeability modeling, and the coupling between microstructural parameters and permeability under water injection conditions is still insufficiently understood. Therefore, this study develops a fractal-based permeability model by incorporating microstructural parameters obtained from CT imaging. Both pore structure complexity and flow path tortuosity are characterized using fractal dimensions. The model is validated using experimental data, providing a quantitative relationship between coal microstructure and permeability and offering theoretical support for the optimization of coal seam water injection technology.

Compared with conventional permeability models, this study explicitly incorporates fractal pore structure and tortuosity into a unified framework, improving the physical interpretability of permeability prediction.

2. Materials and Methods

Coal Sample Preparation

Coal samples were collected from the No. 15 coal seam of the Lutaishan Mine. To ensure the reliability of subsequent microstructural characterization and permeability testing, intact coal cores were obtained using drilling techniques from in-situ coal seams. Samples with minimal weathering and structural damage were selected to preserve their original characteristics.

The collected coal cores were processed into standard cylindrical specimens with dimensions of 50 mm in diameter and 100 mm in height. Both ends of each specimen were ground to ensure parallelism, with an error controlled within 0.1 mm. To eliminate the influence of initial moisture content, all samples were dried in an oven at 80 °C for 24 hours, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Drying Oven

Figure 2: Schematic of Five Coal Core Samples

A total of five specimens (Figure 2), labeled S1 to S5, were selected for further analysis. Basic physical properties, including dimensions, mass, and density, were measured for each sample, the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Basic Physical and Geometrical Parameters of Coal Samples

Sample ID	Diameter/mm	Height/mm	Volume/cm ³	Original Mass/g	Density/kg·m ⁻³
S ₁	49.5	100.5	193.40	293.2	1515.99
S ₂	49.7	100.8	195.55	292.9	1497.81
S ₃	49.8	100.2	195.17	287.9	1475.11
S ₄	49.7	99.6	193.22	287.1	1485.99
S ₅	50	100.4	197.13	290.0	1471.07

CT Scanning and Image Processing

To characterize the internal pore structure of the coal samples, X-ray micro-computed tomography (CT) was employed for non-destructive imaging. The imaging principle is based on the attenuation of X-rays when passing through materials with different densities, which can be described by the Beer–Lambert law.

The scanning was conducted using a V|tome|x S240 industrial CT system, as shown in Figure 3. Considering the relatively large size of the samples and the need to capture multi-scale pore structures, micro-CT scanning was adopted. The main scanning parameters were set as follows: voltage of 130 kV, current of 110 μ A, and spatial resolution of 57 μ m. A total of approximately 1000 slice images were obtained for each sample.

Figure 3: Industrial X-ray CT Scanning System

The acquired CT images were processed through a series of steps, including noise reduction, image cropping, threshold segmentation, and three-dimensional reconstruction. Median filtering was applied to reduce noise while preserving structural details. Image segmentation was performed based on grayscale thresholds, which were calibrated using experimentally measured porosity values to ensure accuracy.

Following segmentation, pore network models were extracted using the maximum inscribed sphere method, as shown in Figure 4. This approach allows for the quantitative characterization of pore bodies and throats, including their size distribution and connectivity. Based on the reconstructed pore network, key microstructural parameters were obtained, including effective porosity, fractal dimension, tortuosity fractal dimension, and pore throat radius.

Figure 4: Pore Network Skeleton Diagram

Permeability Measurement

Permeability tests were conducted using a steady-state water injection method under triaxial stress conditions. The experiments were carried out using a multi-field coupled system capable of controlling stress and fluid flow, as shown in Figure 5.

Before testing, all samples were fully saturated by immersion in water until the mass variation between successive measurements was less than 0.1 g, indicating complete saturation. Each sample was then sealed with a heat-shrink tube and placed in the testing chamber, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Multi-Field Coupled Gas-Water Injection Experimental System for Coal Reservoirs

Figure 6: Schematic of Coal Sample Wrapped with Heat-Shrink Tubing

Figure 7: Constant-Pressure Water Injection Mode

During the test, a constant axial stress of 5 MPa and a confining pressure of 5 MPa were applied. The water injection pressure was increased stepwise from 1 MPa to 4 MPa, as shown in Figure 7. At each pressure level, sufficient time was allowed for the flow to reach a steady state. The outflow was collected and measured over time to determine the steady-state flow rate. The permeability was then calculated based on Darcy's law using the measured flow rate, pressure difference, and sample geometry, as expressed in Eq. (1):

$$k_w = \frac{q_w \mu_w L \times 10^2}{A(p_1 - p_0)} \quad (1)$$

where k_w is the permeability of water ($10^{-3} \mu\text{m}^2$), q_w is the volumetric flow rate measured under atmospheric pressure (cm^3/s), μ_w is the dynamic viscosity of water at the test temperature ($\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$), L is the length of the coal sample (cm), A is the cross-sectional area (cm^2), and p_1 and p_0 are the inlet and outlet pressures (MPa), respectively.

As shown in Figure 8, the experimental results showed that the permeability values varied among the samples, reflecting the heterogeneity of their internal pore structures. These results provide a basis for subsequent model validation.

Figure 8: Comparison of Measured Permeability for Different Coal Samples

3. Model Development

Fractal Characterization of Pore Structure

The pore–fracture system in coal exhibits strong heterogeneity and multi-scale characteristics, making it difficult to describe using conventional geometric parameters. Fractal theory provides an effective framework for characterizing such complex porous media due to its ability to describe self-similarity and scale invariance. According to fractal theory, the relationship between a structural measure and the observation scale can be expressed as a power-law function. In porous media, the cumulative number of pores with radius greater than or equal to r follows a fractal scaling relationship:

$$-dN(r) = D_f r_{max}^{D_f} r^{-D_f-1} dr \quad (2)$$

where D_f is the fractal dimension and r_{max} is the maximum pore radius. This relationship indicates that smaller pores are more numerous, reflecting the self-similar distribution of pore sizes.

To facilitate permeability modeling, the pore system is simplified as a bundle of capillaries with different radii. The coal matrix is treated as a homogeneous medium at the macroscopic scale, while its microscopic heterogeneity is characterized by effective porosity, pore size distribution, and fractal parameters.

Fractal Representation of Tortuous Flow Paths

In real porous media, fluid flow paths are not straight but exhibit tortuosity due to the irregular geometry of the pore network. The tortuosity is defined as the ratio of the actual flow path length L_t to the straight length L_0 :

$$\tau = \frac{L_t}{L_0} \quad (3)$$

Based on fractal theory, the flow path length can be described as a function of the measurement scale:

$$L_t(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon^{1-D_T} L_0^{D_T} \quad (4)$$

where D_T is the tortuosity fractal dimension and ε represents the characteristic length scale. By relating the scale to pore size, the tortuosity can be expressed in terms of pore radius, allowing the incorporation of flow path complexity into the permeability model. A larger D_T indicates a more complex and tortuous flow path, leading to increased flow resistance.

Construction of Representative Geometric Parameters

To establish a quantitative relationship between pore structure and flow behavior, a representative elementary volume (REV) is introduced. Within the REV, pores with radii in the range of r to $r + dr$ are assumed to follow the fractal distribution described in Eq. (2).

The total cross-sectional area of pores perpendicular to the flow direction can be obtained by integrating the contribution of pores at different scales:

$$A_p = \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} \pi r^2 (-dN) \quad (5)$$

By incorporating the fractal pore distribution, the pore area can be expressed as a function of fractal dimension and pore size limits.

The effective porosity φ_e is then defined as the ratio of pore area to the apparent cross-sectional area A :

$$\varphi_e = \frac{A_p}{A} \quad (6)$$

To simplify the pore system, an average pore radius is introduced based on the fractal distribution, allowing the complex pore network to be represented by an equivalent capillary bundle.

Furthermore, to ensure consistency between two-dimensional image-derived parameters and three-dimensional flow modeling, the geometric relationships are transformed into a three-dimensional framework using the volumetric fractal dimension D_f .

Through these steps, the geometric parameters of the REV are systematically linked to fractal characteristics, providing a foundation for permeability modeling.

Derivation of the Permeability Model

By integrating the pore size distribution and tortuosity relationships into the capillary bundle model, the total flow rate can be obtained by summing contributions from all pore scales.

Assuming laminar flow of a single-phase fluid in a capillary, the flow rate through a single pore can be described by a modified Hagen–Poiseuille equation:

$$q(r) = G \frac{\Delta P (2r)^4}{\mu L_t(r)} \quad (7)$$

where r is the pore radius, ΔP is the pressure difference, μ is the fluid viscosity, and L_t is the actual flow path length.

By integrating the contributions of all pores within the REV and incorporating the fractal distribution of pore sizes and tortuosity, the total flow rate can be obtained. Combining this with Darcy's law, the equivalent permeability of the coal can be expressed as:

$$k = \frac{2^{D_f-4} \pi^{\frac{1-D_f}{2}} \varphi_e^{\frac{1+D_f}{2}} (D_f+1)^{\frac{D_f+5}{2}} (3-D_f)^{\frac{1+D_f}{2}}}{(1-\varphi_e)^{\frac{1+D_f}{2}} D_f^{D_f+3} \cdot r_{\max}^{1+D_f-D_f} r_{\min}^{D_f-D_f-3}} \quad (8)$$

This model quantitatively relates permeability to key microstructural parameters, including effective porosity, fractal dimension, tortuosity fractal dimension, and pore throat radius.

Model Validation

Due to the limited number of samples, the results primarily demonstrate the applicability of the proposed model rather than its universality.

To validate the proposed model, the calculated permeability values were compared with experimental measurements obtained from water injection tests, the results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Calculated and Measured Permeability of Coal Samples

Sample ID	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅
Calculated Permeability/mD	0.06049	0.01676	0.3551	0.14254	0.01314
Measured Permeability/mD	0.06529	0.01527	0.32253	0.13434	0.01481

The results show that the predicted permeability values are in good agreement with the measured data. The relative errors for the five samples are 7.35%, 9.76%, 10.10%, 6.10%, and 11.28%, respectively, with an average relative error of 8.92%.

Figure 9: Comparison of Calculated and Measured Permeability

As shown in Figure 9, most data points are distributed close to the 1:1 reference line, indicating a strong correlation between calculated and measured values. The model performs well across low and medium permeability ranges, while slight deviations are observed at higher permeability levels. However, no systematic overestimation or underestimation is observed.

These results demonstrate that the proposed fractal-based permeability model has good predictive capability and can effectively capture the influence of microstructural characteristics on coal permeability. However, due to the limited number of samples, the results primarily demonstrate the applicability of the proposed model rather than its universality.

4. Conclusion

In this study, the relationship between coal microstructure and permeability was systematically investigated based on CT imaging and fractal theory. A fractal-based permeability model was developed by incorporating pore size distribution and flow path tortuosity, enabling a quantitative description of fluid flow behavior in complex pore–fracture systems.

The model was validated using experimental data obtained from steady-state water injection tests. The calculated permeability values show good agreement with the measured results, with an average relative error of 8.92%, indicating that the proposed model has reliable predictive capability.

The results demonstrate that permeability is positively correlated with effective porosity and pore throat radius, while negatively correlated with volumetric fractal dimension and tortuosity fractal dimension. These findings highlight that both pore structure characteristics and flow path complexity jointly control permeability behavior in coal.

However, due to the limited number of samples, the present results mainly reflect the applicability of the proposed model rather than its universality. Future work should focus on expanding the sample size and considering more complex geological conditions to further improve the robustness and generalization of the model.

Overall, this study provides a physically interpretable framework for linking coal microstructure to permeability, which can offer theoretical support for the optimization of coal seam water injection processes.

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